

#25

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

**ECOCYCLE PLANNING
(PRIORITISING TASKS)**

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>At any stage in a project, foreseeing and mitigating unintended impacts.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small to mid-sized multi-actor group.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required, although brainstorming of unintended impacts (which may be unknown to actors) is required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>1.5-3 hrs mins (depending on group size & extent of discussion).</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials. At least one facilitator is required.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools #2, 11, 12.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: [Cory Billingsley on Unsplash](#)

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- To identify possible unintended impacts.
- To facilitate participants to generate hypotheses regarding the causes and effects of actions, which may lead to unintended impacts.
- To facilitate participants to continuously reflect and evaluate the decision-making process regarding the choice of project actions, revising and adapting their plans.

Background and Logic

'Ecocycle Planning is about exploring what it is that you're keeping in the air (but shouldn't), and what it is that you aren't (but should)' (Overeem, 2018).

Interactive innovation is experimental and requires reflexive decision-making rather than rigid plans. Creating supporting spaces for actors to work together co-creatively is paramount, and many of the tools in this handbook are oriented to evaluating, assessing, and enhancing those spaces, as well as increasing reflexivity in decision-making. However, it is also important to monitor the 'unpredictability' of spaces where interactive innovation occurs: it can make planning and assessment of activities challenging because innovation processes are (and should be) continuously evolving. While Tools

#11 & #24 periodically and reflexively assess how actions are giving rise to intended/unintended impacts, this tool assists actors involved in interactive innovation to assess their activities and focus on the more important ones.

Overeem (2018), referring to the useful [Liberating Structures](#) toolbox, refers to a 'metaphor from nature' to explain ecocycle planning that resonates with the process of interactive innovation:

'Plants, for example, grow from seeds when they land in fertile ground (incubation). When the ground is fertile enough, seedlings will sprout that in turn depend on sufficient sun, shelter and minerals to grow (birth). When these conditions have been met, seedlings grow into plants that bear fruits and/or spread new seeds (maturation). But eventually, even mature plants die and are composted to become energy for new plants. Or their removal simply makes place for new seeds to grow (creative destruction).

The work that we do in daily life can be plotted onto this cycle. We often embark on activities that may become valuable at some point, but require our energy and time to grow. Other activities are more mature in that we can do them without much effort to get a lot of value out of them. But as with plants, sometimes we need to stop activities (destroy them) to make space for something new in our agendas'

The above metaphor underpins the philosophy of ecocycle planning, which supports actors' prioritization of actions in the continuous process of renewal of interactive innovation. Assisting the process of renewal and regeneration is particularly relevant to the LIAISON's objective to 'speed up' the innovation process.

Materials

- Ecocycle planning template
- Flipchart paper
- Sticky notes
- Thick dark markers
- Sellotape

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the exercise.
- Present the tasks/actions generated by Tool#2/#11 in view, with information on who has been assigned to the tasks.
- Provide participants with [Ecocycle Planning Templates](#), printed on A3 size paper.
- Explain the template, referencing the following points:
 - » The interactive innovation process is continuously evolving, and it may be necessary to revise current actions/tasks in terms of what is most important and deserving of resources, currently.
 - » As explained by [Overeem \(2018\)](#), The Ecocycle model has two dimensions:
 - 'Some activities may get stuck in the Poverty Trap or the Rigidity Trap. The first holds the activities that aren't getting the energy and time they need to grow into something valuable, while the second holds the activities that are costing us energy and time while their value is diminished or diminished;
 - As in nature, ecocycles are multi-layered in that every activity on the ecocycle contains another ecocycle, only on a lower level. So one ecocycle may describe your personal hobbies or all the products you're working on as a team. A lower-level ecocycle can describe the activities you perform for one specific personal hobby or one particular product that you're working on. This layering also emphasizes that everything is related. Change on one level impact activities on other levels'.

Ecocycle Planning

Step 2: Population of Template

- Revisit-examine the ideas/tasks/actions for the project as a reminder to participants (originally identified by using Tool#2/Tool#11).
- Each actor (working alone) team of actors (working group) is assigned its own table and the tasks assigned to them in Tool#2/Tool#11 written on sticky notes and affixed to flipchart paper. Each table is issued with one blank Ecocycle Planning template, which they can use/complete collectively if working in groups.
- Participants are invited to place their current tasks on the template (duplicating sticky notes where necessary if working in groups and working on the same tasks), indicating where each task in the Ecocycle currently sits. Actors note their initials or an identifying sticker on the post its, so that actors know which tasks are theirs.
- Participants are asked to add any other tasks/actions (not assigned or identified previously) that they are working on currently.
- Once all actions are entered, participants photograph their actions and optionally send an image to the group facilitator/s for their records (to compare to the revised set of actions in Step 3).

Step 3: Revision of Tasks/Actions

- The facilitator re-explains the ecocycle template, where necessary, and prompts actors to re-examine the tasks they are currently undertaking. Are their tasks,
 - » In the Poverty Trap: activities that aren't getting the energy and time they need to grow into something valuable.
 - » In the Rigidity Trap: activities that are costing us energy and time while their value is diminished or diminished;
- There may be different layers of ecocycles:
 - » One layer may describe personal hobbies, for example
 - » Another layer one particular project
 - » This layering emphasizes that everything is related. Changes on one layer can impact activities on other levels
- Participants are asked to now reconsider any task they think should be revised; and to re/move on the template as necessary. Group discussion is encouraged by the facilitator.

Step 4: Continuous Reflexivity

As the participants continue through the process of interactive innovation, ensure that they are facilitated to continuously re-assess, update and revise their tasks/actions as required at wffurther workshops/meetings.

